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**Exploring Beliefs about English Language Learning Among
Pakistani University Students and Teachers**

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Abstract

This study investigates beliefs about second language (L2) learning among Pakistani English language learners and teachers, focusing on university students and English language instructors in Gujranwala, Punjab. Learners' beliefs significantly influence motivation, strategy use, classroom participation, and eventual language achievement. Using a mixed-methods design, the study employed Horwitz's Beliefs about Language Learning Inventory (BALLI) to collect quantitative data from 211 undergraduate and postgraduate students enrolled in English-related programs at a private sector university. Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews with English language teachers to explore teachers' perspectives regarding students' beliefs and motivations. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS (Version 19), including descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, and comparative interpretation. The reliability of the BALLI instrument was satisfactory (Cronbach's Alpha = .831). Qualitative interview data were analyzed using grounded theory techniques. Findings reveal that Pakistani learners strongly value English for employment opportunities, higher education abroad, social prestige, and personal development. Most participants believed that vocabulary, repetition, and regular practice are central to successful language learning. Students also showed strong motivation to achieve fluency and considered English a symbol of academic success and social mobility. Teachers confirmed that learners are highly motivated, particularly due to instrumental goals such as career advancement and international opportunities. The study concludes that beliefs about English learning in Pakistan are deeply shaped by socio-cultural realities, educational policy, and the status of English as a global language. The findings support the importance of aligning teaching practices with learner beliefs to improve L2 outcomes.

Keywords: L2 learning beliefs, BALLI, English language learning, Pakistani learners, teacher beliefs, motivation, English as a second language

1. Introduction

English occupies a unique and powerful position in Pakistan as a language of education, administration, employment, and social mobility. It functions not only as

an official language but also as a marker of prestige and opportunity. For many students, proficiency in English is directly associated with access to higher education, competitive employment, and international mobility. Consequently, beliefs about learning English as a second language (L2) play a significant role in shaping students' motivation and success.

Beliefs about language learning refer to learners' assumptions, expectations, and attitudes regarding how languages are learned, who can learn them successfully, and what factors contribute to successful learning. These beliefs influence classroom behavior, strategy selection, willingness to communicate, and persistence in language learning. Unrealistic or negative beliefs may reduce motivation and increase frustration, whereas positive beliefs can enhance engagement and confidence.

In Pakistan, despite the central role of English in education and professional life, relatively limited empirical research has examined learners' beliefs about English language learning, particularly in comparison with teachers' beliefs. Understanding these beliefs is essential because mismatches between teacher expectations and student beliefs may hinder effective instruction.

This study examines beliefs about L2 learning among Pakistani university students and English language teachers using Horwitz's (1985) Beliefs About Language Learning Inventory (BALLI). It also explores how cultural context, educational policy, and the socio-economic value of English shape these beliefs.

Second Language Learning

If we talk about the second language acquisition, it is basically the very language which a child acquires after L1 or mother tongue. It is also regarded as L2 or the second language. The second language is also called as the target language which is basically the target of the students after acquiring L1, as languages are divided into two different categories such as L1 and L2. There are a number of ways to acquire a second language but the most common ways are mentioned here.

At first, one can learn a second language by the speakers who speak the very language. At second, a student can acquire a second language if the second language will be the part of his curriculum at school.

If we talk about a second language acquisition of a new born child and the adult one, both acquire a second language at different time periods. It could not be wrong if we

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say that their stages of learning are similar but the period of learning is totally different. Comparatively a young child can learn a second language faster than the adult one, because he is at the initial stage of learning and his perception is very strong as well. The point to be pondered upon is the distinction between the word acquisition and learning.

Acquisition means a higher or lower unconscious effort of acquiring a language. It is not a term rather this word is specially used for children whereas learning means the conscious and deliberate effort of getting the ability to learn the second language. It is thoroughly related to a child's abilities of acquiring L1 and later on L2 with an unconscious effort. With having the hope of enhancing the opportunities as well as possibilities for the adults' process of learning a second language, the researchers have tried to judge different forms of language acquisition in order to find out the prominent distinctions as well as the possible similarities between both these processes of learning.

Moreover, Watson-Gegeo and Nielsen have analyzed the socialization of language. They say that the difference between acquisition and learning is totally wrong. They criticize on Stephen Krashen and his theories of distinction between the process of acquisition and learning.

Furthermore, Watson-Gegeo and Nielsen support other researchers like Borosch and Baughan James who reject the idea that acquisition often occur in a naturalistic setting like for example social surrounding or a particular geographical area whereas they believe that learning occur in a proper and formal setting as at any educational institute. The outcome of Watson-Gegeo and Nielsen (2003) analysis is that the cognition is mainly shaped by the social and cultural setting than by home and school. It means that the class room is an innate part of society and so that class room teaching and learning is mere a sole part of acquiring a language within a vast social context, in which there is not a vivid different between learning and acquisition but the view point of Stephen Krashen is of utmost importance and is indeed worthy as well, because Krashen's research mainly revolves the language acquisition on which he has given many significant theories. Krashen (1983;136) strictly gives emphasis on the distinction between learning and acquisition, because to him both are two different and independent methods of learning a second language. Within the hypothesis of

acquisition and learning Krashen explains the major function of acquisition which he calls as the input and storage of knowledge. Krashen claims that acquisition takes place unconsciously. It means that the very person who is acquiring language either he is male or female does not know that on which specific time and moment he is learning something new. There are some examples which indicate that acquisition takes place in simple situations of everyday life as book reading, watching T.V, listening to the Radio and talking to someone. The study contributes to the literature by validating BALLI in the Pakistani context and by providing comparative insights into student and teacher perceptions of English learning.

This study addresses the following research questions:

1. What beliefs do Pakistani learners of English hold about language learning?
2. Is there any gender difference in students' beliefs about language learning?
3. What beliefs do English language teachers hold about language learning?
4. How do teachers' beliefs compare with learners' beliefs?
5. Can a model explain the relationships among learners' belief dimensions regarding language learning?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Beliefs about Language Learning

Beliefs about language learning are recognized as an important psychological and pedagogical construct in second language acquisition research. Richardson defines beliefs as psychologically held understandings and propositions that individuals consider true. In language learning, such beliefs guide expectations, attitudes, and learning behavior.

Horwitz (1985) pioneered systematic research in this area through the development of the Beliefs About Language Learning Inventory (BALLI), which identifies learner beliefs across five major dimensions: foreign language aptitude, difficulty of language learning, nature of language learning, learning and communication strategies, and motivation and expectations.

Research has consistently shown that learner beliefs shape motivation, classroom participation, and language achievement. Bernat and Horwitz argue that unrealistic beliefs often lead to frustration and reduced motivation. Similarly, Peacock found that both teachers and learners frequently hold rigid beliefs that remain

unchanged even after substantial learning experience.

2.2 Teachers' Beliefs and Their Influence

Teachers' beliefs are equally important because they influence teaching strategies, classroom management, assessment practices, and expectations from learners. Nespor emphasizes that teacher beliefs shape professional decisions more strongly than formal pedagogical knowledge in many cases.

Williams and Burden argue that teachers who understand both their own beliefs and those of learners are better positioned to create effective learning environments. A mismatch between student expectations and teacher practices may create classroom resistance and poor outcomes.

2.3 English in Pakistan

English in Pakistan functions as a language of power, administration, higher education, and elite mobility. Rahman (2007) notes that English is strongly associated with socio-economic advancement and institutional authority. It is widely used in bureaucracy, media, military services, higher education, and professional recruitment. Students often perceive English as essential for obtaining good jobs, pursuing higher education abroad, and achieving higher social status. Mansoor (1993) found that instrumental motivation dominates English learning in Pakistan, where students view English as a practical necessity rather than merely an academic subject.

The implementation of English Medium Instruction (EMI) policies in Punjab further strengthened the importance of English from early schooling. However, challenges such as teacher preparedness, curriculum mismatch, and unequal educational access continue to complicate English language learning.

2.4 Pakistani English and Cultural Context

Pakistani English possesses its own linguistic identity shaped by local languages, cultural borrowing, and contextual adaptation. Kachru and Baumgardner highlight that English in South Asia should not be viewed merely as imitation of native English norms but as a localized variety with its own legitimacy.

Therefore, beliefs about English learning in Pakistan are not purely linguistic but also deeply connected to identity, class, globalization, and educational aspiration.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative component used BALLI to examine students' beliefs systematically, while the qualitative component used semi-structured interviews to explore teachers' perspectives in greater depth.

Mixed-methods research was selected because it allows triangulation and provides a richer understanding of beliefs than a single-method design. Quantitative findings identify broad patterns, whereas qualitative insights explain the reasoning behind those patterns.

4.2 Participants

The study was conducted at a private sector university in Gujranwala, Punjab, Pakistan. A total of 211 students participated in the questionnaire survey. Participants included both BS and MA students enrolled in English-related programs.

Among the participants, 51 were male (24.2%) and 160 were female (75.8%). Regarding year of study, first-year students were 23.7%, second-year students 53.1%, third-year students 18.0%, and fourth-year students 5.2%. BS students constituted 41.7% of the sample, while MA students represented 58.3%.

Additionally, five English language teachers participated in semi-structured interviews.

4.3 Instruments

The primary quantitative instrument was Horwitz's BALLI questionnaire consisting of 35 items measuring beliefs across key dimensions of language learning. Responses were recorded using a Likert-scale format.

The qualitative instrument was a semi-structured interview protocol focusing on teachers' views regarding:

- Learners' beliefs about English learning n- the importance of English in Pakistan
- Teachers' attitudes toward motivating learners

4.4 Reliability and Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 19. Reliability testing showed strong internal consistency with Cronbach's Alpha = .831, confirming the suitability of BALLI for the Pakistani context.

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Descriptive statistics, frequency analysis, and comparative interpretation were used for quantitative data. Interview responses were transcribed and analyzed using grounded theory to identify recurring themes and conceptual categories.

Results

The table below illustrates the statistics of some significant questionnaire items. The mean of item no 31 is 5.10 which is the highest one and its standard deviation is 1.131. Whereas the mean of item number 18 is 4.98 and its standard of deviation is 1.230. Unlike, item number 18, the mean of item number 20 is 4.95 and its standard of deviation is 1.110. Moreover, the mean of the remaining important items is round about 3.65 to 4.93 comparatively, and the standard of deviation of these items is approximately 1.528 to 1.110.

It can be seen in the above mentioned table that the lowest mean is 2.48 which is of item number 15 and its standard of deviation is 1.366.

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation
It is easier for children than adults to learn a foreign language.	4.72	1.373
Some people have a special ability for learning foreign languages.	4.33	1.253
Some languages are easier to learn than others.	4.33	1.369
English is:	3.25	.859
I believe that I will learn to speak English very well.	4.75	1.116
People from my country are good at learning foreign languages.	3.92	1.222
It is important to speak English with an excellent pronunciation.	4.48	1.387
It is important to know about English-speaking cultures in order to speak English.	4.38	1.318
You shouldn't say anything in English until you can say it correctly.	3.65	1.528
It is easier for someone who already speaks a foreign language to learn another one.	4.34	1.187

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People who are good at mathematics or science are not good at learning foreign	3.35	1.509
It is best to learn English in an English-speaking country.	4.77	1.360
I enjoy practicing English with the native English speakers I meet.	4.67	1.268
It's o.k. to guess if you don't know a word in English.	4.14	1.308
If someone spent one hour a day learning a language, how long would it take them to speak the language very well?	2.48	1.366
I have a special ability for learning foreign languages.	3.84	1.264
The most important part of learning a foreign language is learning vocabulary words.	4.79	1.030
It is important to repeat and practice a lot.	4.98	1.230
Women are better than men at learning foreign languages.	3.92	1.517
People in my country feel that it is important to speak English.	4.95	1.110
I feel timid speaking English with other people.	4.01	1.250
If beginning students are permitted to make errors in English, it will be difficult for them to speak correctly later on.	3.80	1.485
The most important part of learning a foreign language is learning the grammar.	4.51	1.271
I would like to learn English so that I can get to know native English speakers better and their cultures.	4.40	1.209
It is easier to speak than understand a foreign language.	4.03	1.369
It is important to practice with cassettes or tapes.	3.97	1.344
Learning a foreign language is different than learning other academic subjects.	4.25	1.263

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The most important part of learning English is learning how to translate from my native language to English or from English to my native language.	4.43	1.163
If I learn English very well, I will have better opportunities for a good job.	4.93	1.262
People who speak more than one language are very intelligent.	4.49	1.366
I want to learn to speak English well.	5.10	1.131
I would like to have friends who speak English as a native language.	4.68	1.296
Everyone can learn to speak a foreign language.	4.33	1.438
It is easier to read and write English than to speak and understand it.	4.44	1.340
Language learning involves a lot of memorization.	4.64	1.197

English is:

	Frequency	Percent
a very difficult language	6	2.8
a difficult language	24	11.4
a language of medium difficult	103	48.8
an easy language	59	28.0
a very easy language	15	7.1

If someone spent one hour a day learning a language, how long would it take them to speak the language very well?

	Frequency	Percent
less than a year	60	28.4
1-2 years	66	31.3
3-5 years	33	15.6
5-10 years	20	9.5
You can't learn a language in 1 hour a day	28	13.3

Qualitative Data Results

The interview data was analysed through Grounded theory. The replies of five teachers to three interview questions were recorded and transcribed. Teacher A responded to first question that the Pakistani English language learners are motivated to learn English because they want to get good job. In response to second question, the teacher A said that English is quite necessary for the people to learn especially in the modern age, therefore, it should be learned by everyone. In the answer of the third question, teacher A replied that English is the most important language to learn and it should be the first priority of the students who are willing to learn a second language. He suggested English language as a second language to the learners.

As far as teacher B is concerned, when he was asked the same questions, he answered the first question that before learning a second language, the learners should get some information about foreign context and the social surroundings as well. Moving towards the second question, he said that everyone should acquire English language as it has become the order of the day. In response to question number three, he was of the view that the English teachers should motivate the students to learn English to get a number of job opportunities.

Moreover, if I talk about teacher C, like teacher A and B, he was also of the view that English should be learnt by everyone in the answer of question number one. In response to question number two, he asserted that everyone should learn English willingly, because it has become the fashion of the day. Regarding question number three teacher C replied that the motivation of teachers can also be proved helpful for the new learners of foreign language.

Similarly, teacher D thought about the first question that the learner's beliefs about learning English are of utmost importance in their learning process. Related to question two, he shared his notion that one should not be in the state of to be or not to be in order to learn English language rather he should make his mind to learn it when the idea of learning English comes to his mind for the first time. For question three he replied that it would be highly unfair if an English teacher does not encourage his students in order to get English language for their bright future.

Furthermore, teacher E answered all the questions in the favour of learning English not only for students but also for teachers as the other teachers said. He was also of

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the view that English is an international language therefore; everyone should learn it as soon as possible in order to survive in the society.

In addition, teacher F was also in the favour of learning English as it has the great influence on one's personality. When teacher F was asked about question number two, he replied that one should not feel timid while learning English rather one should learn it by heart willingly. In the answer of question number four, teacher F suggested that if an English teacher does not persuade his students to learn English as a second language, he should change his behaviour regarding English.

Discussion

In the very chapter I am going to give a detail account of the people's opinion regarding the collected items of the questionnaire. The reader will also find the discussion about the results of the questionnaire items. Some people are of the view that it is easier for children than adults to learn a foreign language because comparatively children can acquire a second language faster than the adults as the children are at the initial stage of learning and their power of learning is stronger as well.

The mean of item number I is 4.72 and its standard deviation is 1.373. Moreover, some groups of people hold the view that some people possess a special ability for learning a foreign language; therefore, such people can learn a second language well as they have innate ability to learn new things. The mean of this very item is 4.33 and its standard of deviation is 1.253.

In addition, it is said in item number 3 that some languages are easier than others. There are many people who think the same. The mean of the group of the people who support the statement is 4.33, and standard of deviation is 1.369.

Furthermore, 59 people say that English is an easy language to learn, and their ratio is 28.0. Actually, they hold this view mere on account of their own experiences. Whereas, only 6 people consider English a very difficult language to learn and their proportion is 2.8. The people who consider that English is a difficult language to learn they are 24 in number and their percentage is 11.4. After that majority of the people who are 103 in numbers think that English is a language of medium difficult. They believe that English language can be learnt if a person can give proper time to learn it. The people who are of the view that English is not so difficult language as it is

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considered, their percentage is 48.8. A sum of 15 people holds the opinion that English is a very easy language to learn and their percentage is 7.1. The mean of this very item is 3.25 and its standard of deviation is .859.

After that item number 5 shows the perception of the people who believe that they can learn English very well. The mean of this statement is 4.75 and the standard of deviation is 1.116.

Next item illustrates the views of Pakistani natives to whom Pakistanis are good at learning foreign languages. The mean of this item is 3.92 and the standard of deviation is 1.222. Whereas, the mean of the very next item is 4.48 and its standard of deviation is 1.387. As a result of people's believe that a good pronunciation is must in order to speak impressive English. The more if I talk about the questionnaire items, item number 8 represents the consideration of the people who claim that the knowledge of English culture is necessary to have before learning L2. The result of this item is 4.38 mean and 1.318 standard of deviation.

In addition, it is mentioned in question (item) number 9 that one should not say anything in English until he can utter it correctly. It is acknowledged by majority of the people as it reduces the ratio of the people who lose their confidence owing to the correctness in pronunciation. The mean of this item is 3.65 and the standard of deviation is 1.528. Another item shows the idea of the people that the person, who has discovered a second language, can easily learn the third language as well. The mean of this specific item is 4.34, and the standard of deviation is 1.187.

Likewise, the natives of the locality are of the view that it is a hard nut to crack for the genius of science and math to learn English. The number of people who think in this way their ratio results in 3.35 mean and 1.509 standard of deviation. There are also some communities in which it is thought learning of English speaking will be better in the English society. The mean of this particular item is 4.77 and standard of deviation is 1.360. Moreover, it can be seen in the next item that people prefer practicing in English with meeting English speakers. The percentage of such people is resulted in 4.67 mean and standard of deviation is 1.268. Afterwards, some learners of L2 like to guess if they cannot understand the real meaning of English diction. The mean of this question is 4.14 and standard of deviation is 1.308.

Similarly, it is believed in a couple of people who are 60 in number, that if someone

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practices to speak English one hour each day, he will learn to speak English properly in less than a year, and their percentage is 28.4. Whereas, 66 people hold the opinion that if someone spends one hour a day in learning L2, he will learn to speak the foreign language in 1-2 year, and their proportion is 31.3. Next a frequency of 33 people claims that if one gives one hour of one's time to learn L2 every day, one will be able to learn the very language in 3 to 5 years, and their percentage is 15.6.

Minimum 20 persons consider that if a learner tries to give sixty minutes of his time to learn English daily, it will be easy for him to learn English in 5-10 years.²⁸ People think that one cannot learn a language in one hour a day because to them it needs a lot of time to acquire L2, and their percentage is 13.3. The aggregate of the people who share their views regarding item number 15, results in 2.48 mean and 1.366 standard of deviation.

More, some people think that they have special ability to learn a foreign language, their mean is 3.84, and their standard of deviation is 1.264. Likewise, the next question indicates the thinking of the people who are of the view that the most significant part of learning L2 is learning its vocabulary. The very view of the people is collected in 4.79 mean and 1.030 standard of deviation. The next item shows the opinion that repetition and practice work a lot in acquiring a second language, especially English. The mean of this item is 4.98, and its standard of deviation is 1.230. Unlike, the previous item, the mean of question number 19 is 3.92 and its standard of deviation is 1.517, because it is believed by a few people that women are far better than men in learning foreign languages. The next statement of the selected questionnaire exposes the common view of Pakistani people that learning of English language is their basic need. The mean of this specific item is 4.95 and its standard of deviation is 1.110. The more if I explain is that a sum of people in Pakistan feels shy in speaking English. Their ratio is resulted in 4.01 and their standard of deviation is 1.250.

It is shown in item number 22 that if the new learners at first make errors in English, it is highly difficult for them to speak correctly later on. The mean of this statement is 3.80 and its standard of deviation is 1.485. After that some people consider the grammar of L2 prior to learn the foreign language and the mean of this point is 4.51 and its standard of deviation is 1.271. Moreover, some people like to

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learn English in order to understand the native speakers well, their ratio is 4.40 mean and standard of deviation is 1.209. Next it is mentioned in the item number 25 that the speaking of English language is easier than its understanding. The mean of this item is 4.03 and the standard of deviation is 1.369. In the same way, it is illustrated in item number 25 that the cassettes can be proved helpful in order to practice English speaking. This saying is significant as it has 3.97 mean and 1.344 standard of deviation.

Whereas the next statement is the indication of people's saying that the learning of a foreign language is thoroughly different than learning other academic subjects. This item is justified by its 4.25 mean and by its standard of deviation as well which is 1.263.

Further, one school of thought is of the opinion that the most convenient way of learning is to learn the art of translating through Pakistani native language to English and then from English to the native language. The validation of this statement can be understood by its percentage which is shown by 4.43 mean and 1.163 standard of deviation. Likewise, another school of thought has made up a thought that if a person learns English language to groom his personality, he will get a number of job opportunities in the near future. The mean of the very item is 4.93 and its standard of deviation is 1.262. The next item is based on the perception of some Pakistani natives who are of the view that to speak more than one or two languages shows one's intelligence as the career oriented people remain in the quest of learning especially English language.

The truth of this statement lies in its 4.49 mean and 1.366 standard of deviation. Afterwards, it can be seen in item number 31 that the ratio of mean 5.10 and 1.131 standard deviation people not mere desire to learn English speaking rather they think that they ought to speak English fluently in order to meet the requirement of the age. Furthermore, it can be noticed in the very next item that some people like to have friendly terms with English natives because they consider it more helpful in the learning of L2. The people who think in this way, their mean is 4.68 and standard of deviation is 1.296

Similarly, it comes to the reader's eye that mean 4.33 and standard of deviation 1.438 consists on the proportion of the people who consider that everyone can learn to speak

English. Proceeding towards the second last item which is based on the consideration of the people of a geographical area who think that the reading and writing of English language is easier than to speak and understand it. The validity of this saying is proved by the result of the statement which is 4.44 mean and 1.340 standard of deviation.

Finally, the gathered data of questionnaire ends with the recommendation of some people that memorization is a lot more compulsory in order to have an easy access to L2 as the learning of English language has become the order of the day. It can rightly be said that it is the dire need of everyone in order to cope with the modern tendency.

The universality of the very item can be well understood by the exposure of its mean and standard of deviation which are 4.64, and 1.197 respectively.

Teachers' Views on Learning English as a Second Language

Teacher (A) is of the view that the students should have a keen desire to learn the art of English speaking. To him, the practice of English speaking is must if the learner wants to speak English well as it is universally believed that practice makes a man perfect. The more the learner will try, the more he will be fluent in English. He is of the opinion that the people of his country have the desire to speak English properly as English has become the official language of the country and its worth is also justified by its universality as it is also acknowledged as lingua-franca throughout the whole world. He thinks that the most significant part of learning a foreign language is to first have command on its vocabulary even of its most common words.

He claims that children an acquire a second language earlier than adult ones, as they are at the initial stage of learning and their power of learning a language is stronger as compared to the elder ones. Moreover, he holds the opinion that the students should not utter a single word of English before learning its correct pronunciation because in this way they are criticised by others and become a laughing stock as well. Further, he has the notion that the learners who are good at Mathematics and Science, it will be a bit difficult for them to learn English language including its grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary as well. Afterwards, teacher (A) gives his opinion that English is not a difficult language to learn as it is generally considered in Pakistani societies. People mere make their opinions on account of rumours regarding

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learning English and they take the learning of English language difficult by relating it to the foreign context which is the hamartia of Pakistani natives. At last, he gives suggestions to the learners that if they do the practice of English speaking every day even mere for one hour, it will be proved profitable for them in the future.

As far as teacher (B) is concerned, he does not mere think rather believes that some students possess the innate ability of learning a foreign language. It is up to the teacher that how much he tries to motivate the students in order to give way to their special abilities. He thinks that the beliefs of the learners should also be taken into consideration in their learning process because if they are given a chance to give an outlet to their personal views and ideas regarding learning English as a second language. They will learn English easily. He believes that there are a lot of benefits of English language as it is required in every field of life like for example banking, marketing, teaching etc.

Moreover, he likes it because of the uniqueness of the subject as well as of the language. English is an international language and has a great impact on the mind of the people not only in our country but all around the globe. It is the trend of the day. Everyone wants to speak and learn it in order to develop his personality.

He says that English is considered as the most difficult subject in our country, because the rate of literacy is less than the rate of illiteracy. People just listen the rumors and lose their hearts in spite of learning it. Being an English teacher, he can help the students who feel great difficulty in learning it. He claims that he can solve all of their problems regarding the subject. He shares that it was his desire to serve his country and pay social services, and he thinks that teaching is the best profession through which he can fulfilhis aim. He believes that English is the only subject through which he can serve more as compared to other fields.

Whereas teacher (C) thinks that the most important function of an English teacher is to teach his pupils the facts and beliefs regarding learning English which are wise and sensible one. Being an English teacher the teacher C shares the dilemma of the teachers that today a teacher is deprived of liberty in teaching the students. He is not expected to teach what he believes rather only what his culture wants him to teach. He is of the view that this very attitude can never produce good learners of English language. He believes that the teacher should be impartial in his teaching. He says that

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the main role of a teacher lies in developing the inborn qualities of the students regarding learning a foreign language, and then to encourage their qualities.

Moreover, he says that a teacher should motivate the students for learning English language by exercising it in the class room. He should teach the students in such a way that the students' interest in acquiring English language, should be developed, and in this way they will learn English by taking interest in it not only to cover their syllabus but also in search of knowledge.

In the same way, the teacher (D) believes that the students who want to learn English are of the view the English is of great importance and its influence is very strong in Pakistani society. Teacher D in the answer of question number two thinks that English is the only language which is considered by the students a tough language, but he thinks that they can be guided and motivated in order to learn English language. He thinks that English language is not as tough as it is believed in our society. He also believes that there are so many advantages to learn English language, because in this way, one can get a lot of opportunities in this society. He says that we should first of all learn English and then should go for any other language to learn.

Further, teacher D is of the view that the students who think that English is an easy language, can be taught properly and easily because they are already motivated and have the notion that it is one of the easiest language in the world. In this way, teacher D wants everyone to learn English as early as possible. In a nutshell, he suggests, and motivates his students in order to get and acquire English as a second language.

Moreover, if we talk about the teacher (E) who is the last participant, he holds the same opinion as other teachers believe. In response to all these questions, he highly motivates the students for learning English and in rest of the two questions he also believes the same as other teachers believe.

Through the interviews conducted by five different teachers and questionnaires collected by two hundred plus students, it can be said that the result of the interviews and questionnaires is almost same. All the participants as well as teachers are in favour of learning English language in order to survive not only in this particular society but in all over the globe.

Conclusion

The study explores students and teachers' beliefs about English learning in Pakistani context. The main purpose of the current study was to investigate the validity of BALLI beliefs in Pakistani context. Moreover, in start of the thesis, cultural needs of Pakistan regarding learning English were discussed. Many problems in order to learn English language have been discussed by various writers' point of views. It is seen that in the recent years Government of Punjab has introduced EMI (English Medium Instruction) for a better future to the students. The policy was held in the primary schools for the beginners so that the students get no difficulty in learning L2 even in the early ages. The main point of the study is to analyze students and teachers' behaviour regarding learning of English (L2). It will also be proved helpful in learning English at different institutes. The purpose of the study is to investigate the beliefs of learners and teachers regarding learning of English as a second language. It also includes comparison of Pakistani natives on theoretical and curricular relevance regarding learner's beliefs, and the contribution of L2 in learning English processes. Significance of the study is elaborated in this chapter through research work. Through questionnaires we find that the people of our society feel fear of learning English and it has dominated their mind set too. Teachers and students who speak good English are considered different as compared to the people who cannot speak English well.

The results of 211 questionnaires and teachers' interviews explored beliefs about English language learning in Pakistani context. The results were almost same got by the questionnaires from the students and interviewed by the teachers. The strategies of the people regarding learning English L2 are also discussed properly. In the questionnaire each question is indicated or pointed out as item statistics and the mean of individual item with standard of deviation were also transcribed. In this chapter it was shown that the highest mean was 5.10 with standard of deviation 1.131. Whereas the lowest mean of the item number 15 was 2.48, and its standard of deviation was 1.366. A brief summary of the most significant items was also mentioned in the chapter number 4. In this chapter it is shown that many of the Pakistani want to speak good English, and consider that practicing it a lot could gain them a better career. English language is thought an easy language for the children as compared to the adults. The people of sciences are not good in learning other

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languages. English is considered a language of difficult medium. Teachers were interviewed and their views regarding learners' learning problem were also mentioned in detail in the same chapter. The teachers also prefer English to learn as a second language so that the students can get good jobs in the same field.

The study explored that Pakistani second language learners are keen to learn English language because they want to get jobs, as well as want to go abroad for higher studies. The learners also consider English as an important language in Pakistan. They want to speak English language fluently. The learners strongly believe that they will get a good job, high status and respect in society after getting a degree in English language. The interview data revealed that English language teachers believe that second language learners of Pakistan are highly motivated to learn English.

References

- Alanen, R., (2003). A sociocultural approach to young language learners' beliefs about language learning. In P. Kalaja & M. F. Barcelos(Eds.), *Beliefs about SLA: New research approaches* (pp. 55-85). Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Atlan, M. Z. (2006). Beliefs about language learning of foreign language-major university students. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 31(2), 45-52.
- Banya, K., & Chen, M. (1997, March). *Beliefs about language learning: A study of beliefs of Teachers' and students' cultural setting*. Paper presented at the 31st annual meeting of the teachers of speakers of other languages, Orlando, FL.
- Bernat, E. (2004). Investigating Vietnamese ESL learners' beliefs about language learning. *English Australian Journal*, 21(2), 40-54.
- Bernat, E. (2007). EFL learners' and teachers' mismatched beliefs about language learning in an academic setting. In C. Gitsaki (Ed.), *Language and languages: Global and local tensions* (pp. 171-184). Newcastle, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Cai, W., & Sciban, S. (2010). A preliminary investigation of listening strategies used by heritage and non-heritage Chinese language learners at the beginner's level. *Journal of Chinese Language Teaching*, 7(2), 39-63.
- Caracelli, V. J., & Greene, J. C. (1993). Data analysis strategies for mixed-method evaluation designs. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 15(2), 195-

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

207.

- Creswell, J. (2002). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Creswell, J. (2003). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J., & Plano Clark, V. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Christison, M. A., & Krahnke, K. J. (1986). Student perceptions of academic language study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 20(1), 61-81.
- Cui, Y. (2005). Review of the topics of general interest within the past 20 years in the field of teaching Chinese as a second language. *Applied Linguistics*, 1, 63-70.
- Cui, Y. & Lapadat, J. (2009). *Code-switching by Chinese English-as-a-second-language students: A multiple case study of contexts and strategies in computer-mediated communication*. Saarbrücken, Germany: Lambert Academic Publishing
- Dörnyei, Z. (1990). Conceptualizing motivation in foreign-language learning. *Language Learning*, 40(1), 45-78.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Doughty, C., & Williams, J. (Eds.). (1998). *Focus on form in classroom second language acquisition*. Ernst Klett Sprachen.
- Gaies, S. J., Galambos, A., & Cornish, Y. (1999, March). *The metacognitive beliefs of Russian learners of English*. Paper presented at the annual conference of the American Association for Applied Linguistics, Stamford, CT.
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Horwitz, E. (1985). Using student beliefs about language learning and teaching in the foreign language methods course. *Foreign Language Annals*, 18, 333-340.
- Horwitz, E. (1987). Surveying student beliefs about language learning. In A. Wenden J. Rubin (Eds.), *Learner strategies in language learning* (pp. 119-132). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Horwitz, E. (1988). The beliefs about language learning of beginning university

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- foreign language students. *The Modern Language Journal*, 72, 283-294.
- Horwitz, E. (1999). Cultural and situational influences on foreign language learners' beliefs about language learning: A review of BALLI studies. *System*, 27(4), 557-576.
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. A. (1986). Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70, 125-132.
- Johnson, K. E. (1994). The emerging beliefs and instructional practices of preservice English as a second language teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 10(4), 439-452.
- Johnson, R. B., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2004). Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come. *Educational Researcher*, 33, 14-26.
- Kalaja, P. (1995). Student beliefs (or metacognitive knowledge) about SLA reconsidered. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 5(2), 191-204.
- Kalaja, P., (2003). Research on students' beliefs about SLA within a discursive approach. In P. Kalaja & A. M. F. Barcelos (Eds.), *Beliefs about SLA: New research approaches* (pp. 87-108). Dordrecht : Kluwer.
- Kern, R. G. (1995). Students' and teachers' beliefs about language learning. *Foreign Language Annals*, 28(1), 71-92.
- LeLoup, J. (1995). Preservice foreign language teacher beliefs: Mythology 101. *Expectations of Excellence: Preparing for Our Future*, 137-146.
- Levine, G. S. (2003). Student and instructor beliefs and attitudes about target language use, first language use, and anxiety: Report of a questionnaire study. *The Modern Language Journal*, 87(3), 343-364.
- Maftoon, P., & Shakouri, N. (2012). Relationship between learners' beliefs system and the choice of language learning strategies: A critical study. *International Journal of Research Studies in Language Learning*, 2(2), 39-48.
- Murphey, T., & Arao, H. (2001). Reported belief changes through near peer role modeling. *TESL-EJ*, 5(3), 1-15.
- Murray, H. G. (1991). Effective teaching behaviors in the college classroom. *Higher education: Handbook of theory and research*, 7, 135-172.
- Oxford, R. L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- Peacock, M. (1999). Beliefs about language learning and their relationship to proficiency. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 9(2), 247-263.
- Peacock, M. (2001). Pre-service ESL teachers' beliefs about second language learning: A longitudinal study. *System*, 29(2), 177-195.
- Truitt, S. N. (1995). *Anxiety and beliefs about language learning: a study of Korean university students learning English* (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations and Theses database. (UMI No. 3001368).
- Wang, J., & Intaraprasert, C. (2009). The mismatch of beliefs about learning English between Chinese university students and teachers. *Sino-US English Teaching*, 6(9), 21-31.
- Wong, M. S. L. (2010). Beliefs about language learning: A study of Malaysian pre-service teachers. *RELC Journal*, 41(2), 123-136.
- Yang, N. (1999). The relationship between EFL learners' beliefs and learning strategy use. *System*, 27(4), 435-600.
- Young, D. J. (1991). Creating a Low-Anxiety Classroom Environment: What Does Language Anxiety Research Suggest? *The Modern Language Journal*, 75(4), 426-437.
- Zar, J. H. (1999). *Biostatistical analysis*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Zhang, L., & Wang, B. (2002). Analysis of anxiety of learning Chinese and achievements among international students in China. *Language Teaching and Research*, 1, 36-41.
- Zheng, H. (2009). A review of research on EFL pre-service teachers' beliefs and practices. *Journal of Cambridge Studies*, 4(1), 73-81.